

Science

DISEASES DURING CAMPING IN BNCC

M Ashraful Kabir ^{*1}, M Harun or Rashid ²

^{*1}Lecturer and PUO in BNCC, Cantonment Public School and College, Saidpur Cantonment
5311, Bangladesh

²Major, BNCC, 34 BNCC Battalion, BNCC mor, R K Road, Rangpur, Bangladesh

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Abstract

During camping in BNCC all cadets face some medical problems. Their problems not more worsen but this may lead misunderstanding about the training of BNCC. Our cadets are normally fit because when they get admitted in BNCC there was a criterion that they are medically fit or not. The major problems such as asthma, big birth defect, nasal and ear problems not allowed in BNCC. In camping they get excellent medical services so that they not fall serious problems. In BNCC camping cadets get always fresh food and water and moreover they take bathe regularly. After march past or exercise they take oral saline, so not shown any dehydration. Some simple injuries for wearing tight shoes and for crawling knee and elbow injury are common. All trainings are held in winter season so for cold weather their exercise not considered burden. Cadets sweating are very few so they get more energy in training. In noon they perform playing and every night the cultural show rehearsal runs. Mostly all cadets live well any camping without any major diseases. The writers of this paper both they attend several camping with high ages but not got any major diseases during camping (Plate 4).

Keywords: BNCC; Camping; Injury; First Aid.

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1. Introduction

Bangladesh National Cadet Corps (BNCC) leads future leader which is very important for a nation. Physical fitness comes by this. After completion the BNCC for two years they get chance to be an army officer easily. This is a great opportunity to do something for our country. Each year cadets get four chances to take training. Capsule training twice a year, one annual and one central camp is sufficient for the cadets. Moreover BNCC cadets get chance to attend unarmed combat training (self Defence). For BNCC admission all cadets are selected by good at English and physical and mental fitness. So when they go any training not fall any diseases. Simple

injury or environmental changes sometimes causes only acidity or digestive disorder. After physical activities then excess sweating they take oral saline so this situation not comes bad. Due to fresh food and all day long medical services during camping cadets' life not threatened. Moreover for winter camping they gets comfort in all schedules.

2. Materials and Methods

Cadets

Near about 150 male and female cadets attend any training (Plate 1). Their living places are different. They attend classes about primary treatment of the diseases and personal hygiene by expert (Plate 2). During this training huge knowledge they get on human health and after finishing this training they apply all those in their family.

Physicians

Some physicians perform duty only for cadets' problems. In weekend day (Friday) all cadets wash their cloth and clean outside their living area. So, mosquito or other insect not enter their places. Fogging for mosquitoes is applied around their places.

Medical team

If any serious incidents happen in training currently a medical team referred cadets to concern authority by ambulance or release them to their house after getting good treatment. But this incident is very few (Plate 8).

3. Results

Table 1: Common problems during camping and antidote

Sex	Incident	Why Happen?	Treatment/Advice
male/female	injury	exercise	bandage, pain killer
male/female	acidity	food	antacid
male/female	skin disorder	unhygiene	ointment/cream/advice
female	periodic problem	natural/unhygiene/exercise	hygienic advice
male/female	fever	environment	antibiotic
male/female	dyspepsia	food	changing feeding habit
male/female	epigastric pain	food	changing feeding habit
male/female	diarrhoea	food	advice (liquid food), orsaline
male/female	body pain	exercise	pain killer
male/female	dust in air	exercise	anti allergic
male/female	allergy	dust/food/sun	anti allergic
male/female	constipation	not take adequate water	advice
male/female	headache	periodic fever/huge work load	pain killer
anxiety/depression	psychological	psychological	advice
male/female	sore throat	commanding voice	advice (vocal rest)
male/female	knee pain	injury	advice (not perform in march past)

male/female	tinnitus	firing	some yoga/motivation
male/female	ringworm	fungus	antifungal medicine
male/female	animal bites (snake, insect, rat/shrew, dog etc)	animals in camping area	advice, dog- anti rabies vaccine, hygiene
male/female cadets shelter	fire in living place	electric wire, laundry, electric devices	advice

Table 2: Problem associated first aid

Diseases/Problems	First Aid
suspended breathing	ventilation, loosen dress, artificial breathing
bleeding	immobilize such organs, not give any food
shock	warmth
burn	1 st degree- skin dry and red 2 nd degree- wet skin and fluid discharge 3 rd degree- fat, bone, nerve and muscle injure (non-adhesive sterile dressing)
eye	eye wash by distilled water for 20 minutes, not use cotton bud for removing dirt from the eye
heat stroke	patient in cool place
fracture	splint, control bleeding, elevate such parts, ice pack, immobilize such parts, check the circulation in affected area, rest and assure
poisoning	give water/milk
snake bite	not elevate the bitten limb
choking	hug with patient, pressure on back shoulder

Diagram 1: From highest to lowest problems in camping

Plate 1: Morning shows the day

Plate 2: Physical contact may fatal

Plate 3: Animals are vector

Plate 4: Adjutant and PUO (writer)

Plate 5: Waiting for food

Plate 6: Need more conscious in open area

Plate 7: Raw fishes with blood

Plate 8. Medical camp

4. Discussion

In human body diseases are three types- when any germs invade within the body and spread or affect any organ this is infectious disease; by sneezing or coughing a person spread huge germs in the air and infect somebody this is communicable disease (Plate 3, 5, 6,7) and if diseases spread through physical contact this is contagious disease. Alcohol based sanitizer not effective on cryptogerm (hidden germs). Diarrhoeal patient not perform in swimming (www.cdc.gov/parasites/crypto). In any camping about 12 peoples need for 2-3 days minimum 27 items in first aid (Girl Guides of Canada). In outside there are four major reasons for disease spreading like person-to-person, food, water and animal (vector) (Plate 3). During camping lyme disease (bite of deer tick), norovirus (vomit and diarrhea) and whooping cough (pertussis) are very common. For the awareness for the campers it's good to mention sick and well cabin in front of the tent (Bureau of Communicable Diseases and Emergency Response, 2013). When insects bite it may lead shock and there huge possibility for severe allergic reaction. It stunk on throat it's beneficial to drink cold water and ice compress. In injury any food colour or lipstick is useful (Scouts be prepared, 2000).

5. Conclusion

Without being trained nobody can flourish their lives. Physical activity promotes good health and without good health not possible to do good thing. During training some injuries and for changing daily life some minor problems or diseases may happen but this is not hazardous. If anybody takes any training solely he/she not get hurt and smoothly passing their training period. Personal hygiene is the main precaution to pass disease-free life in any camping.

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*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: harun264@yahoo.com